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Where is my Family? Contemporary Uyghur Activism in the Transnational Diaspora

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the shifting dynamics of Uyghur diaspora activism, tracing its trajectory from widespread silence before 2017 to a surge of family-centered mobilization between 2017 and 2020, followed by a subsequent ebb and re-fragmentation. We argue that family has simultaneously functioned as the Chinese state's most effective lever of transnational repression and the diaspora's most effective tool of activist mobilization. Threats to relatives at home created a climate of fear that silenced Uyghurs abroad; yet the sudden severing of contact with family after 2017 undermined that control and compelled thousands to speak out. This rupture precipitated the emergence of a family-centric form of campaigning that altered the global visibility of the Uyghur issue and legitimacy of Uyghur activism within and beyond the diaspora. Since 2020, the resumption of tightly monitored contact with family members has re-muted many voices, even as others remain engaged. This arc in Uyghur political mobilization offers insights into how family ties can simultaneously constrain and propel diaspora activism – an area that remains understudied – and foregrounds the intimate scales through which transnational repression operates and diaspora activism can emerge and take shape.

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Introduction

“Where is my family?” became the simplest and most powerful question of Uyghur diaspora activism in 2019. It appeared on placards and livestream platforms from Almaty to Istanbul, Paris to Oslo, and Washington, to Toronto (Figure 1). As a hashtag, #Where-IsMyFamily circulated widely, pushing the Uyghur issue into popular and mainstream media. This family-centered refrain captured a major shift in diaspora activism that followed a profound rupture inside the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region (XUAR).²

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¹Musapir is the pen name of an Indigenous Uyghur diaspora scholar.

²The Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region is an administrative entity established in 1955 by the Chinese Government. This region is known to many Uyghurs outside China as *weten* (homeland) or East Turkistan. The region has been colonized by China-based powers since the mid-eighteenth century and referred to as Xiyu (Western Regions) and Xinjiang

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FIGURE 1. Zubayra Shamseden (left) and Elfidar Iltebir (right) at the “Stop the Uyghur Genocide Rally” organized by the Uyghur American Association on October 1, 2021. Credit: Kuzzat Altay.

In 2014, the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) severely intensified its surveillance and assimilation policies in Xinjiang. This included the mass incarceration of Uyghurs, Kazakhs, and other minority groups inside a vast system of camps and prisons, which peaked between 2017 and 2020.³ During this time, many Uyghurs abroad lost contact with their relatives inside Xinjiang. The state also expanded its transnational repression of Uyghurs through surveillance, harassment, coercion, and threats. A 2023 study documented 7,108 cases across forty-four countries worldwide, 6,870 of which had occurred since 2014.⁴ Even under these conditions, after 2017, thousands of overseas Uyghurs and Kazakhs who had previously remained silent began to speak publicly about the repression experienced by their families and communities in Xinjiang, and a new cohort of young, well-educated, and tech-savvy Uyghur activists emerged. The testimonies and activism of these individuals proved crucial in building knowledge and international recognition of the repression and camps in Xinjiang.⁵

In 2020, many detainees were released and highly controlled contact with family members in the diaspora was allowed. However, repression in Xinjiang did not cease; it changed form. The militarization of the region was reduced while the grid of administrative surveillance through government agencies like neighborhood committees (*shequ*) was tightened and the use of minority languages was curtailed.⁶ Imprisonment remained widespread; coerced labor and assimilationist pressures continued. Yet

(new dominion). Older names that cover large parts of this region include Alte Sheher (Six Cities) for the southern parts and Zhungaria for the northern parts.

³Zenz 2019; Roberts 2020, 47; Byler et al. 2021, 7–15; Byler 2022. The Chinese authorities have represented the camps as voluntary de-extremification schools or vocational training centers.

⁴Lemon et al. 2023. The intensification of transnational repression was facilitated by new digital technologies and economic and political ties between China and countries hosting migrants and refugees from the region. See also Tobin and Elimä 2023; Uluyol 2023.

⁵Frangville 2022, 414–415.

⁶This information is taken from interviews with recently arrived Kazakhs from Xinjiang in Alamy in fall 2024 and winter 2025 as well as with Uyghurs living in Sweden, Turkey, and Germany who had visited relatives in Xinjiang in 2024 and 2025. The interview data has been triangulated with Chinese media reports and social media content.

activism slackened and the diaspora re-fragmented into a smaller core of highly engaged activists and a renewed silent majority.

This article traces the arc of these shifts in Uyghur diaspora activism, from widespread silence before 2017 to a surge of family-centered mobilization between 2017 and 2020, followed by an ebb in and re-fragmentation of the activist landscape since 2020. Previous studies have highlighted the role of digital media, particularly social media platforms, in the surge of Uyghur grassroots activism.⁷ This was undoubtedly an important factor in the late 2010s. However, as political scientists Obert Hozdi and Özge Zihnioğlu point out in their work on social media activism in Africa, “social media, like any medium of information production, dissemination and mobilization, is not a causal agent.”⁸ By this they mean that technologies amplify or accelerate processes whose roots lie elsewhere. Social media matters for speed and reach, but in the Xinjiang context it amplified a process rooted in family ties, which also is at the heart of diaspora members’ retreat into silence since 2020. It is their family and kin networks in Xinjiang that the Chinese state has weaponized to silence the diaspora, and it was the sudden loss of communication and connection with family members that catalyzed new forms of activism.⁹ To make sense of these dynamics, we draw on Wendy Pearlman’s concept of “silencing fear,” which encompasses the bundle of emotions, calculations, and social expectations that encourage people to submit to coercive authority; fear is not simply a feeling but a mechanism that shapes personal behavior, often routinized and reinforced by social ties.¹⁰

Our central argument is that family has functioned as both the Chinese state’s most effective lever of transnational repression of Uyghurs and the diaspora’s most effective tool of activist mobilization. In her pioneering research on diaspora activism during the 2010–2012 Arab Spring, Dana Moss highlights the importance of connections to relatives back home for the extent to which diaspora members chose to speak out against the repressive governments of their home countries, and how and why this can change.¹¹ One of the ways that Libyan and Syrian regimes had exerted control over their diaspora populations was by threatening to punish family members back home.¹² According to Moss, in the wake of the Arab Spring, when regime violence engulfed their relatives, diaspora members “felt released from the obligation to keep quiet in order to protect their loved ones from the threat of repression.”¹³

There are important parallels between the dynamics Moss describes in Middle Eastern diasporas and the role of family in the transformation of activism in the Uyghur diaspora. But there are also significant differences that expand our understanding of the ways in which family connections and kinship can “simultaneously promote and curtail [diasporic] political engagement,”¹⁴ as well as how they can shape the form of engagement.

⁷Witteborn 2022, 161; Musapir and Steenberg 2024b, 154. On the affordance and limitations of digital media in Uyghur diaspora activism and community-building before 2017, see Shichor 2010; NurMuhammad et al. 2016.

⁸Hodzi and Zihnioğlu 2023, 44.

⁹We use the term “family” to refer to the nuclear family (parents, children, siblings, spouses) invoked in activists’ testimonies and slogans, while “kinship” denotes broader networks of relatedness that shape Uyghur social life.

¹⁰Pearlman 2016, 24–26.

¹¹Moss 2022.

¹²Moss 2022, 5, 75–83.

¹³Moss 2022, 25, 94–109.

¹⁴Moss et al. 2020, 746.

Care, waiting, and listening

This article draws on multiple qualitative methods: interviews, participant observation, textual and social media analysis, and group discussions. It grew out of long, complicated, complex, and very human encounters with Uyghur and Kazakh diaspora members rather than a neat research plan. Our analysis is anchored in and motivated by extensive, slow, relational fieldwork, and relations of trust built over time. We carried notebooks more than recording schedules; we learned to wait, to sit in silence, and to close our notebooks when a voice began to shake. In the overlap of the COVID-19 pandemic and the peak of detentions, we found ourselves practicing quiet forms of care—messages, meals, midnights online—as much as methods. Much of that care happened through screens. We kept company on video calls when borders were closed and days felt airless; sometimes we said nothing at all and just let the call run while someone cooked, cried, or tried to sleep.

At the core of our analysis are twelve in-depth interviews with Uyghurs who belong to a new cohort of young, media-savvy activists who started campaigning when their relatives in Xinjiang were detained or disappeared, in most cases after 2017.¹⁵ We also engaged in many informal conversations with these individuals, and compiled articles written by and about them and a further eight activists. Additionally, we reviewed and analyzed thirteen books, most of them autobiographical and co-written by survivors or witnesses in Uyghur, German, French and English, and interviewed five of the authors.¹⁶ To contextualize their individual activism, we also examined twenty-eight Uyghur activist organizations worldwide, analyzing their institutional structures, mandates, and activities. We particularly analyzed their social media activity and attended events they organized. This allowed us to contrast formal organizations with independent activists, many of whom deliberately distance themselves from institutional affiliations.

Also central to our analysis are several phases of participant observation in activist groups in Finland, Germany, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, the United States, and Canada between 2018 and 2025. We attended protests and press conferences, scribbling in the margins of programs, taking notes on the choreography of placards and slogans, and noting when and how “family” was referenced. We archived social media posts with hashtags like #WhereIsMyFamily, #MeTooUyghur, #HearUyghurs, and #SaveUyghur. We also draw on insights from our earlier lengthy periods of fieldwork in Xinjiang between 2008 and 2016. After travel to the region became impossible in 2017, we followed Uyghur life in the diaspora. We went where activism and everyday life unfolded: Istanbul bookshops and Ankara offices, Helsinki apartments and Berlin cafés, Almaty markets and Washington sidewalks, quiet kitchens in Toronto and university towns in the American Midwest. While some of the conversations we had in these spaces were arranged, many unfurled around tea, on long walks, outside consulates, or in the back

¹⁵See Musapir and Steenberg 2024a for a more comprehensive overview of contemporary diaspora Uyghur activism, including the important activities of Kazakhstan-based organization Atajurt and the Xinjiang Victim’s Database (shahit-biz), which had documented the cases of over 87,000 victims of incarceration in Xinjiang as of March 1, 2024.

¹⁶We see life narratives as not only personal histories but also vessels of cultural knowledge, relationality, and responsibility (see Somerville and Justice 2016). The materials we draw on include Kadeer and Cavellius 2009; Hoja 2023; Turkel 2022; Ilham 2015; Hamut 2023; Sauytbay and Cavellius 2021; Idris 2020; Ala 2021; Abdusalam and Bradley 2022; Haitiwaji and Morgat 2021; Chanisheff 2018; Osman 2015; and Tohti 2022.

rows of conferences. Just as often, we joined the digital rooms where posts, placards, and hashtags became testimonies.

Family leverage and diaspora silence

Before 2017, engagement in activism among Uyghurs in the diaspora was low and fragmented. After the CCP consolidated its control in the region after 1949, thousands of Uyghurs fled to the Soviet Union, Turkey, and India.¹⁷ In the 1950s and 1960s, Turkey became host to a large diaspora community and a center for Uyghur independence activists. Uyghur migration to Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkey, and the Middle East goes back generations through trade, seasonal labor, study, and pilgrimage, as well as political exile. In the 1990s and 2000s, those routes expanded to Europe and North America. More Uyghurs left China for political, educational, or business reasons. Members of the diaspora established a number of important organizations including the World Uyghur Congress and the Uyghur Human Rights Project, which focus primarily on human rights, including minority rights.¹⁸ Despite this history of activism, the plight of Uyghurs in Xinjiang received little international attention before 2017. This was in part because relatively few Uyghurs abroad engaged in activism, even in the wake of increased state repression in the late 1990s and from 2009.¹⁹

In our long-term engagement with Uyghurs abroad from varied social backgrounds, we identified numerous reasons why many had not been involved in activism before 2017. Those who were able to move relatively freely between China and other countries wanted to protect their mobility and, in some cases, their business interests. Those whose legal status was more precarious faced the possibility that they might have to return to China or could even be extradited.²⁰ Moreover, not all diaspora members sympathized with activist causes. Some believed that calls for an independent Uyghur state were unrealistic or even counterproductive for Uyghurs in Xinjiang, while a number of well-educated Uyghurs abroad did not oppose certain Chinese government restrictions on conservative religious practices in the countryside. Like government and party officials, as well as many Uyghur intellectuals in Xinjiang, they viewed Islamic piety movements as a hindrance to development and social stability.²¹

A common thread in the motives of overseas Uyghurs for remaining silent was concern for the safety of their relatives. Chinese authorities would hold relatives of Uyghurs living abroad collectively responsible for what a son or daughter might say in Munich, Ankara, or Washington. When exiled activist Rebiya Kadeer was elected president of the World Uyghur Congress in 2006, three of her children in Xinjiang were immediately placed under house arrest, and later that year one of her sons was sentenced to nine years in prison for “subversion.”²² This high-profile example served as a cautionary tale for many in the diaspora. More generally, police phone calls and home visits to relatives by authorities conveyed the cost of dissent, while Uyghurs traveling abroad for

¹⁷See RFA [n.d.](#)

¹⁸For a more detailed overview of the history of Uyghur activism, see Musapir and Steenberg [2024a](#).

¹⁹Millward [2021](#), 371-375.

²⁰Between 1997 and 2021, at least 427 Uyghurs were returned to China, mainly from Southeast Asia, Central Asia and the Middle East, but also from Germany and Sweden. See Hall and Jardine [2021](#), 4, 21-30; RFA [2012](#).

²¹Musapir and Steenberg [2024b](#).

²²Kashgary [2017](#).

business or studies were often explicitly warned by Chinese authorities, before departure, not to engage with Uyghur exiles or their activities abroad. Many veteran figures in the diaspora preemptively cut off contact with their relatives to protect them, a strategy also used by Middle East diaspora dissidents.²³ For those who prized mobility and the possibility of seeing their parents again, silence was the price. Many younger professionals (including most of our interviewees) tried to steer clear of diaspora organizations and avoid any public commentary, including on social media platforms.

These dynamics are not unique to the Uyghur diaspora. Repressive regimes around the world have used “proxy punishment”²⁴ of family members back home to silence exiles and emigrants. This form of transnational repression, although understudied,²⁵ has been observed in the Middle East, Africa, and Asia.²⁶ In the Uyghur case, the CCP’s leverage of kin as a tool of control is part of a long state strategy to push Uyghur social life toward the domestic and away from public display. Since at least the late Qing period, Xinjiang has been treated as a frontier to be secured and developed.²⁷ By the early 2000s, successive security campaigns had made large parts of public life feel conditional and closely watched. Under these pressures the family increasingly became the center of care, socioeconomic security, and belonging. It also provided the primary space for the retaining of Uyghur traditions, sociality, and identity. Uyghur intellectuals labeled this inward shift “family education” (*a’ile terbiyelesh*), a counterpoint to increasingly Han-dominant state schooling.²⁸

Outside Xinjiang, kinship also anchored life. Up until 2017, immediate family ties, not broader community links, were almost unquestionably tolerated by the party-state, and thus became the main conduit connecting the diaspora to their homeland. Family networks opened up paths for study, work, and business opportunities abroad. By the 2010s, family phone calls (increasingly on WeChat) stitched together diaspora kitchens and Kashgar courtyards. These calls were the main way people abroad learned what was happening at home.²⁹ Just as importantly, it was how members of the Uyghur diaspora maintained a sense of place and personhood.

Within this broader context, family ties became the state’s main handle on those abroad and a particularly effective lever for enforcing diaspora silence. Facilitated by technologies that make surveillance across borders relatively easy, contemporary forms of proxy punishment are an extension of much older practices of “collective retribution.”³⁰ They not only deter people from speaking out but can also be used to secure their cooperation. We talked with several Uyghur students and businesspeople overseas who were coerced into informing on fellow Uyghurs by Chinese intelligence agents.³¹ Most Uyghurs in this position have chosen to remain out of the public eye, but some have publicly told their stories.³² Chinese handlers provided secure messaging apps for

²³Moss et al. 2020, 744.

²⁴Moss 2016.

²⁵Moss 2022, 72.

²⁶Moss et al. 2020, 736. See also Adamson and Tsourapas 2020.

²⁷Cf. Bellér-Hann 2008a, 424; 2015; Leibold 2020; Byler 2021; Salimjan 2021.

²⁸Cf. Muhammet-Imin 2002. This emphasis on family education resonates with findings from Indigenous contexts where settler colonial violence targeted public gatherings, forcing cultural transmission into the home. See Corntassel and Hardbarger 2019 on everyday acts of family education in Cherokee households.

²⁹Moss 2022, 11.

³⁰Moss et al. 2020, 746, 737.

³¹See also Hall and Jardine 2021.

³²Daragahi 2018; Agence France Press 2020.

these coerced informants to report on their compatriots. Widely known cases of such collaboration, along with the fact that some Uyghurs living abroad were able to travel back and forth freely or even received Chinese government scholarships, sparked rampant speculation within the diaspora about who might be a spy. Consequently, many Uyghurs abroad chose to live in isolation from each other to avoid entanglement and scrupulously avoided any connection to activists or Uyghur organizations.

While fear of proxy punishment and mutual suspicion were major deterrents, the general eschewal of politics among many young, well-educated Uyghurs (many of whom would become activists after 2017) was also related to their relative socio-economic privileges. A disproportionate number of young Uyghurs who were able to secure passports and go abroad to study were the children of party members or from wealthy families. While they faced ethnic discrimination and restrictions on political and religious freedoms in Xinjiang, or even had been briefly detained by authorities, they and their families lived relatively comfortably and had more opportunities and leniency within the system than did Uyghurs from rural, poor, devout, or dissident backgrounds.³³ These young people also often became well-integrated in their host societies as students, professionals, or entrepreneurs, just as they had been in Chinese society. Many could travel back and forth to Xinjiang and communicate with family and friends back home; in some cases, their relatives even visited them abroad.

The granting of limited privileges is a powerful tool of control among populations like the Uyghurs who generally suffer discrimination and feel unsafe vis-à-vis the state.³⁴ It is a classic tactic of colonial regimes used to co-opt Indigenous elites.³⁵ At the same time, we should acknowledge the agency of these young, privileged diaspora members. Some had limited sympathy for activism centered on independence and nationalism. But, like many other Uyghurs abroad, they also wanted to protect themselves and their families, as well as safeguard their mobility. The ability to visit their families was hugely important to those who lived abroad permanently. Some of these relatively privileged people have spoken publicly of their onetime dreams of living an “ordinary” life, free from politics, discrimination, and the community responsibility that comes with being Uyghur. One such man has said that he had longed for “a life that doesn’t involve politics, government work or community service.”³⁶ Having grown up in Xinjiang as the son of government employees (with a grandfather who had been sent to a labor camp during the Cultural Revolution), he had been “taught to keep a distance from politics, so I would have a safe and peaceful life.”³⁷ In a 2021 interview, Kuzzat Altay, who was at the time the president of the Uyghur American Association, said he had “wanted to stay away from politics because we suffered a lot as kids.”³⁸ Kuzzat had left China in 2005 after being briefly arrested by state security; he fled first to Turkey and then to the United States in 2008, where he became a successful businessman. His goal, he said, was to live the American dream — “to build a normal life, a normal person’s life: wake up, go to work, hang

³³NPR 2021.

³⁴De Genova 2020.

³⁵Osterhammel 1997, 89-99.

³⁶Uyghur 2019.

³⁷Uyghur 2020.

³⁸NPR 2021.

out with your family.”³⁹ He was only propelled into activism when his father disappeared in 2018.

Rupture, testimony, and solidarity

When Uyghurs (and others) began to be arrested and sent to camps and prisons by the hundreds of thousands in 2017, Chinese authorities went to great lengths to isolate the region and control the flow of information. Measures included mass passport confiscations, severe restrictions on international travel, the recall of many Uyghur and Kazakh students and expatriates (often to detain them upon return), and the severing of contact, in many cases, with anyone outside one’s local area in Xinjiang, as well as with diaspora members.⁴⁰ In most families, communication with relatives abroad ceased entirely in 2017. A survey of the Xinjiang Victims Database indicates that merely having transnational contacts, especially with someone in a Muslim-majority country or in countries with large Uyghur diasporas, was sufficient pretext for detention,⁴¹ even if the contact was a close relative.⁴²

For diaspora Uyghurs, the disappearance of family tore away important elements of their personhood and identity, triggering profound distress, desperation, and psychological suffering.⁴³ It undermined their sense of self and belonging, affecting their material, psychological, and spiritual well-being.⁴⁴ But it also loosened the grip of the silencing fear permeating the diaspora by breaking the logic of “protecting by staying quiet.”

In October 2018, the second author visited Istanbul with Danish documentary filmmaker Anja Dalhoff, who intended to interview survivors of the detention camps in Xinjiang and Uyghurs whose relatives had disappeared back home. Previous experience had shown that getting anyone to speak on camera could be difficult. Yet almost all the Uyghurs they approached were willing to testify and most were happy to do so on camera. Others came forward when they heard about the opportunity via word of mouth, lining up for hours in front of the bookstore where the testimonies were recorded, some carrying their children, others postponing business and family duties. Most of them had not spoken publicly about their experiences before this and almost all gave the same explanation for why they had chosen to speak: they had not had contact with their relatives in more than a year, and did not even know if they were alive.

In most cases, missing family members were alive (though many had suffered incarceration or torture). But the period of uncertainty often stretched for years. Some information trickled out through distant relatives or the small number of camp survivors who

³⁹NPR 2021.

⁴⁰See New York Times 2019 for one of 403 Chinese government internal documents leaked to Times reporters. This document addresses how to handle students returning to Xinjiang from elsewhere in China.

⁴¹A search of the Xinjiang Victim’s Database for cases with the detention reason “contact with the outside world” generated 263 hits as of June 2023; among those, 238 were detained since the start of the Chen Quanguo era in 2016.

⁴²See Hall and Jardine 2021, 31; Sauytbay and Cavelius 2021; Haitiwaji and Morgat 2021.

⁴³This was expressed unanimously in all of our interviews as well as in the diaspora circles where we conducted our fieldwork and have lived for the past eight years.

⁴⁴This dynamic probably exists in most groups, but what makes it particularly pronounced among Uyghurs is the high significance of kinship for them as members of a marginalized group and the characteristics of Uyghur kinship as less based on patrilinear descent and more on interactive relatedness practices than most of the surrounding groups. The practices of Uyghur kinship—especially in the south of XUAR—are more strongly bound up in regular and repeated acts of gift giving and keeping in touch than is the case among groups with a stronger tie to genealogical imaginations like lineage, tribe and clan. See Steenberg 2013, 2018, 2022.

managed to leave China after their release. Their stories, along with satellite imagery and leaked Chinese government documents, helped researchers and journalists piece together an increasingly detailed and bleak picture of what was happening in Xinjiang. But the scarcity of solid, verifiable data left much space for fearful imaginings. A young female engineer in Toronto explained to us in an interview, “while I was reading all the horrible news about the camp system in China and could no longer call my family, I just wanted to make sure my parents were at home and not in the camps.”

With no way to communicate with those back home, the danger of speaking out was no longer concrete or immediate. As the first people started speaking out, others felt a sense of liberation from their former restraint. Years of pent-up frustration and anguish poured out. Thousands provided video or written testimonies, many of which were collected on platforms like YouTube, Facebook, and Twitter, as well as websites such as Shahit.biz (Xinjiang Victims Database), Uyghur Pulse, Atajurt, and the Uyghur Transitional Justice Database.⁴⁵ These testimonies supplied much of the raw material for the activist campaigns that took shape after 2017. They also countered the uncertainty of what was happening – itself a form of violence – with names, dates, and faces.

The widespread, indiscriminate arrests of their relatives in Xinjiang effectively leveled the playing field for most Uyghurs abroad. A shared experience of loss and uncertainty after 2017 created a powerful sense of solidarity that cut across class, ideological, generational, and religious divides that had previously fragmented the diaspora. It alleviated mutual suspicion and envy, undermining the Chinese authorities’ long-used tactics of selective privilege and fear. Previously disengaged relatives of the detained joined long-time activists and, starting in 2018, a range of new activist groups and informal networks formed and grew.⁴⁶ Many who joined campaigns did so while grappling with survivor’s guilt. Speaking out offered both a way to honor missing relatives and to “do something” in the face of powerlessness.⁴⁷ A restaurant owner in Istanbul, unable to reach his daughters, told us he had “nothing left to lose, but possibly a lot to gain” by protesting.

Among those who decided to speak out was a cohort of relatively privileged young professionals, many of whom had previously eschewed politics. These individuals were suddenly confronted with the full brutality of the party-state, now directed personally at them and their relatives. They lost the sense of security and special treatment that their status and apolitical stance had previously afforded. Some spoke openly about this shock. In an interview with *The China Project*, Halmurat described his reaction on learning that his mother had been arrested: “I was like, ‘You made a mistake. You should catch others, but not my mother ...?’”⁴⁸ He had considered his parents model citizens and thus safe; their detention upended this belief. A similar sense of disbelief

⁴⁵For an analysis of several of these digital platforms and the intertextuality and visibility that they afforded, see Witteborn 2022, Chapter 4. For examples of YouTube channels, see Uyghur Pulse (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxtHBfWaWYQPNgfvDvSDn4A>), Atajurt Kazakh Human Rights Serikzhan Bilash (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC5uns79sHr1AZiUw1ikV7PQ/videos>), Witnesses EN (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZc-hx7kFu8uNcxHv092Pmw/videos>), and Testimony Videos (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBQSF5r5HN09cZQLLoL8v9tA/videos>).

⁴⁶New activist groups included, among others, Uigur Hjelpe (<https://uyghurhjelpe.org>), Uyghur Aid (website no longer active), Campaign for Uyghurs in the US (<https://campaignforuyghurs.org>), Uyghur NextGen Project (<https://uyghurnextgen.org/development-projects>), and Tarim Network (<https://www.thetarimnetwork.com/>).

⁴⁷On guilt as a modality of being a Uyghur in the diaspora, see Ala 2021, 32–33.

⁴⁸Shu 2021.

was publicly expressed by including a Uyghur professional now based in North America, whose parents were CCP members and whose close relative a successful entrepreneur and a “model citizen.”⁴⁹ They had traveled freely between China and the US and believed their knowledge of the law and elite connections would protect their family. That changed when their close relative disappeared in 2016, shortly after returning to China from abroad

Halmurat, a Chinese medical practitioner, was one of the first young activists to gain prominence. He had lived quietly in Finland with his family until his parents’ arrests in 2017 and 2018. In May 2018 he posted a video demanding their release; it went viral and sparked a cascade of similar testimonies, which he collected and reposted.⁵⁰ Within months, he was curating hundreds of such stories, co-founding support channels, and fielding desperate late-night messages from people whose parents had vanished. He told us that he had been offered a deal by Chinese diplomats to stay silent in exchange for his parents’ passports, but he had decided to instead deepen his activism, selling his clinic to fund an NGO called Uyghur Aid. Other prominent figures soon emerged, including sociologist Dilnur Reyhan, software engineer Ferhat Jawdat, businessman Kuzzat Altay, researcher Yalkun Uluyol, journalist and researcher Nyrola Elimä, artist Bahram K. Sintash, health scientist Samira Imin, and business analyst Akida Pulat. Established activists like Jewher Ilham, long an advocate for her imprisoned father, also broadened their roles.

The emergence of these young professionals and their family-centered campaigning shifted the terms of Uyghur activism. Unlike earlier exiles who focused their activist work on Uyghur independence, these young activists were less easily painted as “separatists” and “radicals” by the Chinese authorities. Moreover, their language skills, social capital, and digital fluency gave them access to international audiences. In addition to their very personal concern for family members, many of those whom we interviewed believed that if relatives of the detained and disappeared told their stories, publicly pressured Chinese authorities for their release, and demanded accountability, the situation in Xinjiang could improve. Still, going public was rarely easy. Some of the people who talked with us did not go public for months and, in some cases, years after their relatives had disappeared, in some cases seeking diplomatic channels to secure their release. It was only when the anonymous professional mentioned above received news that their relative had been arrested, tried, and sentenced that they decided to speak openly, feeling that there was nothing left to jeopardize.

Family-centered activism

The abrupt severing of contact in 2017 not only suddenly disabled the lever that had kept people quiet, it also set the stage for a family-centered surge in activism, intensely focused on personal stories. This emphasis on family transformed the Uyghur activist landscape, reshaping the attention paid to the plight of Uyghurs and how global publics understood the crisis.

⁴⁹This public person whom we interviewed chose to remain anonymous in this article.

⁵⁰See Frangville 2022.

After 2017, testimonies given by camp survivors and relatives of those who had been detained began to appear in major international media outlets such as *The New York Times*, *The Guardian*, Al Jazeera, and the BBC. Many of these were based on personal videos first posted on social media platforms. A turning point came in February 2019, when rumors spread that the beloved folk singer Abdurehim Heyit had died in a camp.⁵¹ In response, Chinese authorities released a video of Heyit in custody to prove he was alive. Activists then demanded similar proof-of-life videos for their own missing relatives and Halmurat coined the hashtag #MeTooUyghur, which went viral, and later popularized #WhereIsMyFamily. Thousands of Uyghurs were inspired to share their stories. Many filmed video messages directly addressing the Chinese state, pleading for the release of family members or simply for any information about their fate.⁵²

The importance of digital media in catalyzing this wave of community-based activism and amplifying its reach has been noted in previous studies.⁵³ Here we want to emphasize the specific advantages of a focus on family. Merlyna Lim argues that for social media activism to be successful, it must resonate with contemporary popular culture and dominant narratives “endorsed in mainstream media,” avoiding association with actions or ideologies that challenge or subvert dominant master narratives.⁵⁴ The power of family-focused campaigns is their simplicity: the desire to reach one’s mother, father, or child resonated across cultures, humanized the Uyghur crisis, and was less easy for the Chinese authorities to dismiss as separatist, radical, extremist, or anti-Chinese.

As the main unit of reproduction, family is endowed with a legal definition in most modern state constitutions as well as in international law. Family relations, particularly spousal and parental ties, are often bureaucratically sanctioned and carry certain legal rights, duties, and privileges. Moreover, kinship in bureaucratic market societies has ceded many of its economic and political functions to state and market institutions, and increasingly become imbued with emotional and sentimental value.⁵⁵ This emotional content, along with the entitlement of the family to protection embedded in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Article 16.3), makes the concept a useful rallying point for international solidarity movements and activist campaigns. Highly emotive personal testimonies centered on family succeeded in garnering sympathy and solidarity for the plight of Uyghurs from very different groups across the world, including Jewish students who established a movement for Uyghur freedom,⁵⁶ grassroots Muslim organizations,⁵⁷ labor movements,⁵⁸ and Hong Kong activists.⁵⁹ The personal testimonies and focus on family also provided a good base for media content that a global audience could relate to, as demonstrated by coverage in major newspapers and media outlets. In contrast to previous media attention on Xinjiang, which was rare and mostly limited to violent

⁵¹Cf. Jakhar 2019. On Uyghur activists’ use of hashtags see Witteborn 2022, 157–160. Diaspora Uyghurs are of course not unique in adopting hashtag activism. On the affordance and limitations of hashtag activism in Thailand, see Sinpeng 2021; on Zimbabwe and Ethiopia, see Hodzi and Zihnioğlu 2023.

⁵²Yang 2019

⁵³Witteborn 2022; Musapir and Steenberg 2024a.

⁵⁴Lim 2013, 653–654.

⁵⁵Schneider 1968, 48–62; Strathern 1992, 163; Carsten 2005, 15; Pfeffer 2016.

⁵⁶<https://www.influencewatch.org/organization/jewish-movement-for-uyghur-freedom-jmuf/>.

⁵⁷Mirza 2022.

⁵⁸Cf. The Uyghur Solidarity Campaign UK (<https://uyghursolidarityuk.org>).

⁵⁹Wilson 2019.

anti-state or inter-ethnic incidents, reporting focused on Uyghurs and their suffering and gained a global audience. The public was confronted with individuals holding their loved ones' pictures and talking about their mothers, fathers, siblings, spouses, and children with tears in their eyes and desperation on their faces. These narratives and images, as well as the broader body of evidence that was accumulating regarding mass incarceration, intrusive surveillance, and cultural and religious erasure, raised international awareness of the situation in Xinjiang to an unprecedented level.⁶⁰

The family-focused campaigning also spilled over into more general activism based on newfound solidarity. Fighting for contact with family members and for their release from camps can be experienced and portrayed as a very personal issue without many political undertones. A woman in Turkey told us: "When I paused my PhD study and protested in front of the Chinese embassy in Ankara holding the slogan 'Where is my mother?', I wasn't thinking of politics. I was not being an activist for a nation, I was just begging for news." This is similar to how Halmurat described activism. But while Halmurat was clear that his motivation was "to free my parents,"⁶¹ the stories he heard and people he encountered also made him feel an unprecedented connection with what he called, "my people," many of whom were in a far less privileged and more precarious position than him.⁶² When his parents were released in late 2018, he therefore decided to continue to campaign for those still in the camps.⁶³ Other newly prominent voices in the diaspora, such as Ferkat Jawdat and Kuzzat Altay, framed their family-focused activism within a broader human rights discourse, arguing for recognition of the atrocities committed against Uyghurs in Xinjiang as a genocide.⁶⁴

Family-focused activism was also embraced by established Uyghur organizations, which could provide resources and institutional reach. These groups organized public events and lobbying efforts, leveraging the compelling family narrative. As a result, the Uyghur cause and Uyghur organizations became more palatable to foreign governments and NGOs. This coincided with the rise in tensions between the United States and China and the willingness of the Biden administration to fund activism worldwide that compromised China's reputation. The World Uyghur Congress received a boost in funding from the US National Endowment for Democracy (NED) in the years between 2017 and 2024,⁶⁵ and activist initiatives like Palwan Youth Centre in Istanbul, Atajurt in Almaty, and the Uyghur Youth Initiative in Germany likewise received funding from US government sources. Uyghur activist leaders such as Rushan Abbas and her husband Abdulhakim Idris toured several Muslim-majority countries to garner broader support for the Uyghur cause funded by several US government related entities.⁶⁶ Private donations from wealthy overseas Uyghurs increased as well, including from businesspeople who quietly supported the cause while conducting trade with

⁶⁰For further details, see Musapir and Steenberg 2024a, 142.

⁶¹Uyghur 2019.

⁶²Divided Families Podcast 2021.

⁶³Uyghur 2019; Shu 2021.

⁶⁴Amanpour 2019; Altay 2023. For a critical analysis of the shift toward the genocide metanarrative in Uyghur testimony as both empowering and limiting, see Frangville 2022.

⁶⁵This was documented by the WUC treasury team at the WUC 7th General Assembly in Prague in 2021 and the 8th General Assembly in Sarajevo in 2025 and confirmed in conversations with WUC officials. Under the second Trump administration, starting in 2025, support has decreased.

⁶⁶See, the Center for Uyghur Studies 2022a, 2022b.

China.⁶⁷ Funding also began to flow from Islamic organizations, particularly in the Middle East, which helped finance efforts like the Uyghur-language news channel Istiqlal TV and bolstered the largest Uyghur diaspora organization in Turkey, the Uyghur Maarip Birligi.

Retightening the grip of silencing fear

Despite its effectiveness, family-focused activism and the solidarity it generated in the diaspora have proved vulnerable to a renewed instrumentalization of kinship by the Chinese authorities. Starting in 2020, communication with relatives resumed under strict supervision for a rising number of Uyghurs abroad in parallel with the release of many camp detainees. These seem to have been interconnected elements in the Chinese authorities' response to growing international attention to Xinjiang. They were accompanied by a propaganda campaign aimed at discrediting activists, reporters, and scholars who had been raising awareness of what was happening in the region and at promoting a Chinese counternarrative.⁶⁸ As such they can be seen at least partly as a measure of the success of Uyghur activism. But the resumption of contact also allowed the Chinese authorities to re-weaponize family ties. Voices that had been raised since 2017 began to quieten, not because people no longer cared, but because the risks once again became painfully clear. As one young activist explained, once he heard his parents' voices on a monitored call, "my activism softened, not because my convictions changed, but because the cost became legible again."

Many activists faced this dilemma: when loved ones were released and contact re-opened, should they continue to engage in activism? In some cases, heavily scripted proof-of-life videos circulated in Chinese state media, urging activists to desist and, at times, denouncing them as liars. In one video, Kuzzat Altay's elderly father (who had disappeared in 2018) appeared on national Chinese television saying: "Kuzzat has conducted wrongdoings in splitting the country. As long as he is engaging in such kinds of things, he will not be my son any longer."⁶⁹ Talking with us about this video, Kuzzat reflected that his father must have been coerced and said how painful it was that this was how he discovered that his father was still alive. This chilling episode encapsulates how the very emotional factor that made kinship a powerful mobilizing force, propelling individuals like Kuzzat into activism, also makes it a potent tool for state repression. When Ferkat Jewdat finally reached his mother on a US reporter's phone – with no police in the room – she said, simply, "I'm proud of you." For many Uyghurs, that single unscripted sentence did what dozens of staged state-media videos could not: it exposed the coercion behind those clips in which detained parents "condemned" their activist children.⁷⁰

⁶⁷During conversations with eight anonymous businesspeople in Central Asia, Turkey, Europe and North America they unanimously told us that they and others they knew had increased their support for Uyghur activism since 2018.

⁶⁸See Handley 2020. Further relaxation of restrictions on contact since then, as well as increased opportunities for diaspora Uyghurs to visit family members in Xinjiang, are probably also connected to refocused attention on reinvigorating the economy (including through tourism) under Ma Xingrui, who served as Xinjiang CCP Secretary from 2021 to 2025. While also reflecting broader economic challenges across China, economic issues in Xinjiang are not entirely disconnected from activism and its results. In July 2020, the US Government imposed costly sanctions on China's main cotton producer, the Xinjiang Production and Construction Corporation, for human rights abuses. See Maystadt et al. 2024.

⁶⁹See <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/jmogH1dsj8U>.

⁷⁰See Upson 2021 for further examples of proof of life videos and smear campaigns against activists.

Many activists who were able to speak to family members were confronted with pleas to stop their activism. Many Uyghurs abroad have recorded such conversations and shared them with us or with media and human rights groups.⁷¹ Reports we have received describe how calls often took place in police stations or other monitored spaces, such as neighborhood committee offices. Sometimes security officials could be heard in the background or even seized control of the conversation. One woman recalled: “I heard my mom’s voice after three years, through a police WeChat video call. The officer told me directly: ‘Stop talking to reporters if you want your mom to stay at home.’” Even when calls were made from home, activists knew they were monitored. Some conversations carried veiled threats; others offered inducements or reassurances in exchange for silence.⁷² Even seemingly unmonitored contact carried its own form of control: once parents’ voices could be heard again, the emotional cost of risking that fragile connection became unbearable for some. As one activist put it:

The nation [we fight for] is imaginative, subjective – but my family, my parents, are real and tangible. I cannot risk their wellbeing for my nation. So I had to stop my activism once my family were safe at home, just to make sure they could stay there.

The renewal of coercion by proxy has been accompanied by other intersecting modes of transnational repression. Enhanced digital surveillance by Chinese security services has increased the capacity for intrusive monitoring of Uyghurs’ online activities globally and deepened transnational harassment.⁷³ There has also been a renewed push for intelligence: Chinese authorities (sometimes under the pretext of “welfare” checks by local officials) have asked Uyghurs abroad to provide information on key activists and community leaders.⁷⁴ Activist Mamtimin Ala suggests that an internalized defeatism among Uyghurs in the face of such an apparently omnipotent adversary has led to resignation.⁷⁵ As Wendy Pearlman has noted in the context of Syria, fear is not simply a strategy used to control people; it can also be “deeply formative of their sense of self and being in the world,” narrowing the sense that change is possible, “and hence the perceived need to fight for it.”⁷⁶

All these factors – from renewed fear to fatigue and defeatism – have re-opened a division between those committed to continuing the struggle and those retreating into silence. Some of those who have led family-focused campaigns, such as Yalkun Uluyol, Nyrola Elimä, and Kuzzat Altay, have segued into becoming advocates for Uyghur rights or general human rights. They and youth organizations like United Uyghur Youth⁷⁷ and the Uyghur Youth Initiative (UYI)⁷⁸ continue to give the diaspora a fresh face and energy, particularly in their advocacy for language and culture preservation. Others stepped back once their own families were released, or due to personal burnout or conflicts within diaspora circles. Since 2024, a growing number of Uyghurs and Kazakhs deemed “trustworthy” by the Chinese government have been able to

⁷¹See Drum Tower 2023. We have listened to five such recorded conversations, shared with us in confidence.

⁷²Hall and Jardine 2021; Tobin and Elimä 2023; Uluyol 2023.

⁷³Hall and Jardine 2021, 46.

⁷⁴Hall and Jardine 2021; Tobin and Elimä 2023; Uluyol 2023.

⁷⁵Ala 2021, 33.

⁷⁶Pearlman 2016, 25.

⁷⁷<https://www.uniteduyghuryouth.org/>.

⁷⁸<https://uyghuryouth.de/>.

visit, and receive visits from, their relatives in Xinjiang, producing further retreats from activism and reinstating patterns of silence and internal division. In January 2026, the government funded a visit to Xinjiang by more than 40 Uyghur Turkish citizens.⁷⁹

The tension that reemerged between obligations to one's relatives and to one's "people" was voiced poignantly by one of our interviewees, who stopped his activities after being reunited with family members. He explained that he had to protect his family in China and provide for his children: "Some Uyghurs reached out to me and said they were disappointed that I stopped, that I should have continued. But I can't be a national hero. I am a father, and a son too." Veteran activists, who had been buoyed by the dynamism of young campaigners, have become concerned about what this retreat from activism means for the future. For them, the fight is not just for individuals' families, it is for Uyghurs as a people and their freedom.

Nevertheless, the situation today remains very different from that of the pre-2017 era. Despite the retreat of many Uyghurs from activism and a retightening of the grip of silencing fear, Uyghur activists have achieved an unprecedented degree of legitimacy and normalization within the diaspora. Political engagement is still a minority practice, but it is far less stigmatized than it was prior to 2017. We have observed what seems to be a lasting shift in attitudes: even many non-activist Uyghurs now openly discuss the situation in Xinjiang and prospects of an independent East Turkistan, whereas before 2017 these topics were almost taboo. The increase in private Uyghur funding for activist causes and media also signals this normalization. Meanwhile, beyond the diaspora, the family-focused activism of 2017 to 2020 opened doors to deeper institutional embeddedness in host countries and gained the Uyghur movement greater legitimacy on the world stage. This is evident in the issuance of a joint statement on human rights violations in Xinjiang by 51 countries at the United Nations in 2023, establishment in 2021 of the Uyghurs All Party Parliamentary Group in the UK, and implementation of the US Uyghur Forced Labor Prevention Act in 2022 (still in force) and bipartisan Uyghur Policy Act passed by the US House of Representatives in September 2025.⁸⁰

In short, the "managed" reconnection of diaspora members with families back home has re-harnessed kinship as a mechanism of transnational repression by the Chinese authorities. But the unintended consequences of the severance of family ties in 2017 continue to reverberate in the complex and fragmented diasporic terrain of activism and silence.

Conclusion

The trajectory of Uyghur diaspora activism since 2017 shows that the family has functioned as both the Chinese state's primary lever of transnational repression and the diaspora's most effective tool of activist mobilization. Cross-border family ties are not only personal bonds but also decisive political instruments. By weaponizing these ties, the

⁷⁹<https://news.qq.com/rain/a/20260105A02Z7M00>.

⁸⁰We recognize that the Trump Administration has withdrawn support for human rights issues in China and that this has had a direct impact on the Administration's support for Uyghur issues. However, we argue that the increased legitimacy of the Uyghur movement and its claims in broader US policy circles is nevertheless evident in the passing of the US Uyghur Forced Labor Prevention Act, which would have been hard to imagine prior to 2017, and the continued bipartisan support for Uyghur issues. See also Szadziwski 2020.

Chinese authorities have been able to silence many diaspora members; by rupturing them, they inadvertently provoked political mobilization. Attending to family thus sharpens our understanding of diaspora activism, not as a matter of abstract opportunity structures, but as an intimate calculus of fear, care, and obligation.

The centrality of family in the Uyghur case broadens our understanding of the effects of cross-border family ties on both diasporic silence and mobilization. In discussing the Arab Spring mobilization, Dana Moss emphasizes that it was not simply raw emotion or second-hand “excitement” that drove previously silent Syrian and Libyan diaspora members to protest.⁸¹ Crucially, it was the Arab Spring’s disruption of the mechanisms of transnational repression, including proxy punishment, that had previously kept them quiet. Public activism was transformed from a high-risk into a low-risk activity through the escalation of the regimes’ use of repression at home into “collective, arbitrary violence” (lowering the risk to relatives of speaking out) and a perception that the regimes’ reach and capacity for repression in the diaspora had weakened (lowering the risk to self).⁸²

Although there are significant parallels, the picture is more complex in the Uyghur case. While there was a similar escalation of repression into collective, arbitrary violence back home, this was not in response to an uprising,⁸³ and Chinese state power remained as strong as ever, if not stronger. Instead, the loosening of silencing fear among Uyghur diaspora members was triggered by regime overreach: by cutting off contact with family members, the authorities inadvertently shifted the balance in diaspora members’ assessment of the risks to relatives of speaking out or staying silent. This demonstrates how a repressive regime’s overreach can inadvertently disable its own mechanism of control, transforming fear from a silencing deterrent into a catalyst for action. For three years, thousands of diaspora members decided that the potential benefits of going public outweighed the risk of harm and a much larger number of people were drawn into activism than before. In other words, the upsurge in Uyghur diaspora activism between 2017 and 2020 was firmly rooted in the same familial relations that had previously kept people quiet. The fact that other forms of transnational repression intensified in this period illustrates just how central the family lever was; its removal outweighed those other dangers in many people’s calculations.

The Uyghur case also shows that family is not only a key factor in when and why diasporas mobilize, but can also be central to how they do so. After 2017, highly personalized, family-centric activism led by figures like Halmurat Uyghur, Kuzzat Altay, Nyrola Elimä and others gave the diaspora’s struggle a new face and voice. Their approach had extraordinary resonance. It changed the character of diaspora activism and generated international concern and support for the Uyghur cause on an unprecedented scale, with lasting effects in terms of public awareness. However, since this activism was family centered, it has also proven to have significant limits: by reintroducing contact between family members and cross-border mobility, the Chinese state has been able to retighten the grip of silencing fear. The resulting division that has opened in the Uyghur diaspora since 2020 shows how family ties may sit uneasily alongside broader

⁸¹Moss 2022, 96.

⁸²Moss 2022, 25–26.

⁸³In this and other respects the rise in grassroots Uyghur diaspora activism is also quite different in both form and dynamics from the Hong Kong diaspora’s participation in Hong Kong’s 2019 pro-democracy movement. On the latter, see Shum 2023.

political projects like nationalism or independence, especially when people are effectively forced to choose between their family's safety and being politically active. The Uyghur case thus forces us to reckon with the intimate scales at which repression works, and the equally intimate scales at which activism can emerge. Paying attention to the role of family in diaspora activism reveals not just a story of repression and silence, but a critical analytic for understanding repressive state control and the transnational struggles against it today.

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